

ISic1648

I.Sicily inscription 1648

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐν[θάδεκεῖταιΘεο]
2. δούλη [---]
3. τελευτο[ῦσαέτων][έγεννήθη]
4. μὲν τῆ ὑπ(ατείῃ) [ΑύρηλιανοῦΑύγ(ούστου)τὸβκαὶΚλαυδί]
5. ου Καπιτω[λείνουτῶνλαμπ(ροτάτων)έτελεύτησεδὲ]
6. τῆ πρ(ὸ) ς νων[ῶν---με]
7. τὰ τὴν ὑπα[τεῖανὈνωρίουΑύγ(ούστου)]
8. τ(ὸ) ια κ(αὶ) Κουϛ[ταντίου τὸ β]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Here lies Theodoule, having died, after [?] years, born in the 2nd consulate of Aurelianus Augustus and Claudius Capitolinus of the most illustrious, but having died 6 days before...after the 11th consulate of Honorious Augustus and the 2nd of Constantius.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645087

PHI 316250

PHI 331399

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Vatican. At no.415a

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